

Project Title	Foodways: Exploring household and community food practices
Status	Returned for revision
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Applicant Status	Staff (Senior Lecturer in Human Resources and Organisational Behaviour)
Department	Management
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Name of Funder	Bbsrc-Biotechnology & Biological Sciences Research Council

Ethical Review Application ER/ES483/6 (continued)

Project Description

Foodways: Exploring household and community food practices is a research study that is part of the broader £6M UKRI-funded research programme 'Co-production of healthy, sustainable food systems for disadvantaged communities'. This study is focused on an in-depth qualitative study of a small sample of residents of Tower Hamlets and Brighton and Hove working with our partners WEN (Women's Environmental Network) and BHFP (Brighton and Hove Food Partnership). The study encompasses tried-and-tested research methods in food studies known as a food methodological toolkit: interviewing participants and observing during shopping (shop-alongs) household cooking (cook-alongs), their procurement practices (fridge stories), and their meal and shopping mapping (Joosse & Marshall, 2020).

The aim is to illuminate the lived experience of food procurement, preparation, and consumption through talk and embodied routines and sensory practices. Theorists note that observing food related practices can reveal data about food related routines, habits and everyday practices which augment and extend the verbalised data from interviews which tend to focus on the meaning and significance of the practices for individuals.

The multi-method approach fills in the gaps of our knowledge about the reality of 'what goes on' in everyday life which is much less possible if we rely on interviews or on a single method.

Some of the methods will take place in public or semi-public spaces such as shops and meeting rooms but others will be in people's homes. This will raise different ethical issues which we outline below.

This research study is part of the bigger UKRI-funded project. Dr Katerina Psarikidou and Dr Elaine Swan are the project research investigators based at the University of Sussex. Based on the principles of research co-production, the project is envisioned to provide citizens of socio-culturally diverse communities with choice and agency over the food they consume, the chains through which they access their food, and the policy frameworks that are needed to support the vision of a more inclusive and socio-environmentally just agri-food system for all.

Ethical Review Form Section A (ER/ES483/6)	
Question	Response
>> Checklist	
A1. Will your study involve participants who are currently or potentially vulnerable or unable to give informed consent or in a dependent position (e.g. people under 18, people with learning difficulties, over-researched groups or people in care facilities)?	No
A2. Will participants be required to take part in the study without their consent or knowledge at the time (e.g. covert observation of people in non-public places), and / or will deception of any sort be used? Please refer to the British Psychological Society Code of Ethics and Conduct (or similar guidelines) for further information.	No
A3. Unless specifically and clearly consented (e.g. a media release form), will it be possible, through a research output, to identify participants in any way? (This does not include taking email details for participant prize draws or identifying participants from signed consent forms or holding identity encryption spreadsheets that are stored securely separate from the research data).	No
A4. Might the study induce psychological stress or anxiety, or produce humiliation or cause harm or negative consequences beyond the risks likely to be encountered in the everyday life of the participants?	Yes
A5. Is there a risk that the research topic might lead to disclosures from the participant concerning their beliefs, involvement in illegal actions or any other activities that may represent a threat to themselves or others?	No
A6. Will the study involve collecting any personal special category information* in a form that could allow the participant/ participants to be identified? [* identifiers relating to race, ethnic origin, politics, religion, trade union membership, philosophical beliefs, genetics, biometrics, health, sex life or sexual orientation]	Yes
A7. Will any drugs, placebos or other substances (such as food substances or vitamins) be administered as part of this study and will any invasive or potentially harmful procedures of any kind will be used?	No
A8. Will your project involve working with any substances and / or equipment which may be considered hazardous?	No
A9. Will your study involve the taking and/or storage of human tissue that falls under the Human Tissue Act (HTA)? http://www.sussex.ac.uk/staff/research/governance/erp_overview/humantissue	No
>> Risk Assessment	

A10. If you have answered Yes to ANY of the above questions, your application may be considered as HIGH risk. If, however you wish to make a case that your application should be considered as LOW risk please enter the reasons here. Researchers should note that SREOs or C-RECs may decide NOT to agree with the case that you have made.

We will protect data and comply with the UK Data Protection Act (2018) as outlined below.

There is potential for participants to experience some anxiety or stress about their food practices, food poverty, food relations and understandings. The lead researcher has received training in counselling skills and is aware of the importance of maintaining boundaries with participants and for the wellbeing of both parties. By employing qualitative research methods which have a more open structure, and can be guided by the participants, the researchers will encourage participants to raise themes that are of importance in their own lives, making it clear that activities can stop or be redirected at any time. The team will have a list of contacts

that may be
able to provide
help in relation
to emergency
food aid and
possible
disordered
eating.

Ethical Review Form Section B (ER/ES483/6)	
Question	Response
>> Data Collection and Analysis (Please provide full details)	
B1. PARTICIPANTS: How many people do you envisage will participate, who are they, and how will they be selected?	We envisage we will recruit up to 10 participants in Tower Hamlets and again in Brighton and Hove. They will either be residents of St Georges Estate, Shadwell or participants in the Affordable Food Projects of the Brighton and Hove Food Partnership. They will be selected on the basis of their connection to these sites, and their ability to participate in one or more of the methods.
B2. RECRUITMENT: How will participants be approached and recruited?	They will be recruited through our current networks including our two partners WEN and BHFP. We will provide a copy of the information sheet to the partners and our networks. At the start of meeting with each participant for the first time, we will brief on the ethical process, re-provide information sheets and informed consent forms or where necessary due to technology or language skills, a verbal consent. The participants will have the opportunity to raise any questions about the project. They can decide which methods they would like to participate in. Participants will also receive a shopping voucher as recompense/remuneration for their participation in the research. The precise amount will depend on which methods the participants undertake but likely to be 15-20 pounds per method.
B3. METHOD: What research method(s) do you plan to use; e.g. interview, questionnaire/self-completion questionnaire, field observation, audio/audio-visual recording?	We plan to use a food studies toolkit (Joosse & Marshall, 2020): interviews, non-participant and participant observation, shop-alongs, fridge talks (discussions about food items in peoples fridges), cook-alongs, researcher-taken photographs, food diaries, and map-drawing exercises that explore participants food procurement journeys around their neighbourhood. Examples of these food maps include: routes of food shopping journeys in neighbourhoods; ; a sketch of their staple food, its ingredients, and where they are sourced; The researchers will also take field notes, photographs, audio and video recording and observations that will form part of the analysis. Video recordings will be used for the to provide more complete data for the study. These will focus on practices and not the participants, although full anonymity cannot be guaranteed. We will not photograph or video non-participants in the research. Depending on the COVID situation, we may run some of these on zoom, following the University procedures for storing zoom recordings.
B4. LOCATION: Where will the project be carried out e.g. public place, in researcher's office, in private office at organisation?	The fieldwork will take place at Tower Hamlets or Brighton and Hove. The fridge talks, cook-alongs, map drawing exercises will take place in the participants kitchen and eating areas. The shop-alongs will take place in the local food shops and food markets, and the semi-public / public space in between them. Depending on COVID, some may take place on zoom.

<p>B5. PARTICIPANT WELLBEING: Will the study involve engaging participants in the discussion of potentially distressing or sensitive topics? (e.g. sexual activity, drug use, ethnicity, political behaviour, potentially illegal activities). If so, please set out how you will manage the well-being of participants.</p>	<p>There is potential for participants to experience some anxiety or stress about their food practices and understandings through the course of the research. The researchers are aware of the importance of maintaining boundaries with participants, for the wellbeing of both parties. By employing a participant led structure in the methods, the researcher will encourage participants to raise themes that are of importance in their own lives, making it clear that activities can stop or be redirected at any time. Given the existing relationship with WEN and BHFP, all participants will be directed towards appropriate support services, should anything arise within interviews that may be distressing for participants. This includes but is not limited to: Access to emergency food provision; support with eating disorders and support with mental illness. The researchers and local gatekeepers are aware of organisations which could provide further help should signposting be required.</p>
<p>>> Confidentiality and Anonymity</p>	
<p>B6. Will questionnaires be completed anonymously and returned indirectly?</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>B7. Will research data only be identifiable by a unique identifier (e.g. code/pseudonym)? If Yes, please explain how this will be attributed in B11a below.</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>B8. Will lists of identity numbers or pseudonyms linked to names and/or addresses be stored securely and separately from the research data? If Yes, explain how this will occur in B11a below.</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>B9. Will all place names and institutions which could lead to the identification of individuals or organisations be changed unless this is consented to explicitly in the consent form?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>B10. Will all personal information gathered be treated in strict confidence and never disclosed to any third parties?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>B11. Can you confirm that your research records will be held in accordance with data protection regulations? (http://www.sussex.ac.uk/ogs/policies/information/dpa)</p>	<p>Yes</p>

B11a. Please explain how ANY identifiable personal and/or research data will be managed and securely stored ensuring that participants have given appropriate informed consent for this.	The names of all participants in the study will be anonymised in order to protect their identities although the limitations of this will be discussed with them given that photographs and recordings could lead to identifications. All data will be managed by the researcher and securely stored and transferred using OneDrive. Project passwords will be pre-set and will contain a combination of at least eight alphanumeric and symbolic characters. Once uploaded to OneDrive, original copies of data will be securely deleted from local storage locations. The shared project workspace on OneDrive will be maintained, organised and updated by the researcher, who will do weekly checks on version control, archiving, monitoring and tidying. All raw data files will be named with anonymous unique IDs and a password-protected database will keep record of links between unique IDs and personal data. Shared folders containing raw data will have access limited to the research team.
B12. Do you intend to use the research data for any purpose other than that for which consent is explicitly given? If so, please explain below	N/A
B12a. If you answered NO to any of the above in this section (or think more information could be useful to the reviewer) please explain here:	
>> Informed Consent and Recruitment of Participants	
B13. Will all respondents be given an Information Sheet and be given adequate time to read it before being asked to agree to participate?	Yes
B14. Will all participants taking part in an interview, focus group, observation (or other activity which is not questionnaire based) be asked to sign a consent form? If you are obtaining consent another way (such as verbally), please explain under B17 below.	No
B15. Will all participants self-completing a questionnaire be asked to show consent to participate by a specific and identifiable action? (Give details in B17 below)	N/A
B16. Will all participants be told that they can withdraw their participation at any time during the research and can ask for their data to be destroyed and/or removed from the project until it is no longer practical to do so?	Yes
B17. If you answered NO to any of the above in this section (or think more information will be useful to the reviewer) please explain here:	We have included a verbal consent form in our submission as some participants don't have the technology to print documents or sign pdfs especially if we have to run any of the methods on zoom due to Covid.
>> Context	
B18. Is DBS (Disclosure and Barring Service) clearance necessary for this project? If yes, please ensure you complete the next question.	No
B19. Are any other ethical clearances or permissions (internal or external) required? Please see the help text (i) for further details.	No

B19a. If yes, please give further details including the name and address of the organisation. If other ethical approval has already been received please attach evidence of approval, otherwise you will need to supply it when ready. (You do not need to provide evidence of a current DBS check at this point).	
B20. Does the research involve any fieldwork - Overseas or in the UK?	Yes
B20a. If yes, where will the fieldwork take place? If undertaken overseas you must attach an OTSSRA form. In the event that the Foreign and Commonwealth Office has specific travel warnings in place for the country (ies) to be visited you will also need to provide a detailed risk assessment. https://www.gov.uk/foreign-travel-advice	The fieldwork will be in shops and homes in Brighton and Shadwell.
B21. Will any researchers be in a lone working situation?	Yes
B21a. If yes, briefly describe the location, time of day and duration of the lone working. What precautionary measures will be taken to ensure safety of the researcher(s)?	Some fieldwork to be undertaken by lone researchers will be during usual work hours in public places. For private space research, researchers will work in pairs so that there are not lone researchers in people's homes.
>> Any further concerns	
B22. Are there any other ethical considerations relating to your project which have not been covered above?	Yes
B22a. If yes, please explain:	As the research is focused upon peoples' relationships with and understandings of food, it is possible that the discussions themselves might raise topics that are potentially emotionally difficult or sensitive for the participants. The lead researchers have experience of working and researching within socially deprived environments and they are particularly sensitive to the potential vulnerabilities of participants. Elaine Swan has received training in counselling skills and all researchers have experience of studying food lives and food poverty issues and are aware of the importance of maintaining boundaries with participants, and for the wellbeing of both parties. By employing these research methods and an open structure to the discussions, the researchers will encourage participants to raise themes that are of importance in their own lives, making it clear that activities can stop or be redirected at any time. As reflexivity is of the utmost importance throughout the research process, the researchers will maintain a research diary where they explore ethical issues as they arise and which will serve as a means for them to constantly reflect upon the research process and to share these reflections with colleagues in the research team.

Indicative questions for fridge/cupboard talks:

- Can you tell me about how you use your fridge/cupboards?
- How do you organise what goes where?
- Do you do this work yourself or do others help?
- What is your favourite item to cook with in your fridge?
- How often do you purchase this item?
- Which items are more challenging to get?
- Is there an item which you are always running out on and find yourself having to replace?

Indicative questions for cook-alongs:

- What are your “staple” or most regular foods and meals?
- What ingredients do you use for this meal?
- How often do you have this meal?
- Where do you find these ingredients?
- What is your favourite ingredient to cook?
- How often do you make this meal?
- Do you like to eat it? /
- What is it that you like about it?
- Do you like to prepare and cook it?
- Can you substitute other ingredients?
- Do you sometimes share this meal for any of your relatives and/or friends?
- Do you ever prepare foods together with your extended family and/or friends?
- How did you learn how to cook this meal?
-

Indicative questions for shop-alongs

- Could you tell me where we are going on this shopping journey?
- Do you always take the same journey?
- How often do you go on this journey?
- How often do you shop for food?
- How do you decide what to buy on your regular shops?
- Why do you choose these particular shops or markets or food banks to get your food?
- Why have you bought X, Y and Z?
- Is it difficult to carry some ingredients?
- Are there any ingredients that you find difficult to get?
- Do you find any challenges with your regular food shop?
- How do you usually get there?
- What’s the best thing and the worst thing about your shopping?
- How long have you lived in this neighbourhood?

Indicative questions for map drawing exercises

- Could you draw a line showing the journey from your home to the food shops/markets/food banks that you regularly go to?
- Can you map out a regular and a special meal and the ingredients used on the map?
- Could you mark with a dot on this map of your neighbourhood your favourite food shops/markets?
- Can you map places you might get takeaway or restaurant foods? Could you mark with a dot on this map of your neighbourhood the places that you are important or special for your daily life?

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

Study title: Foodways: Exploring household and community food practices

INVITATION

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide whether to take part, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully.

WHAT IS THE PURPOSE OF THE STUDY?

The purpose of this study is to understand more about peoples' food practices in the home and neighbourhood.

WHY HAVE I BEEN INVITED TO PARTICIPATE?

You have been invited to participate because you are an adult resident of either London Borough of Tower Hamlets or city of Brighton and Hove. We are interested in people's understandings of food and we think you will have ideas and experiences which we think are important for researchers and policy makers to understand.

DO I HAVE TO TAKE PART?

No! It is up to you to decide whether to take part. If you do decide to take part, you will be given this information sheet to keep and will be asked to sign a consent form. You are however still free to withdraw at any time and without giving a reason.

WHAT WILL HAPPEN TO ME IF I TAKE PART?

You will take part in one or more of the following activities with one or more of the researchers:

- *Fridge/cupboards talks* - discussing food items and storage practices in your fridge/cupboards
- *Food maps* – *mapping* your food shopping journeys and the items in chosen meals
- *Cook-alongs*– preparing a meal that you regularly have
- *Shop-along* - going on your usual food shop

During these activities, researcher(s) will accompany you, while taking notes, videos and audio-recordings and photographs with your consent. Participants will receive a small recompense in the form of a shopping voucher for their time and any expenses.

WHAT ARE THE POSSIBLE DISADVANTAGES AND RISKS OF TAKING PART?

The primary disadvantage of participating in this study is the time taken to participate. Participating in the research is not anticipated to cause you any discomfort. The potential physical and/or psychological harm or distress that can be generated by discussing food will be kept to the minimum through the activities chosen, and the experience of the researchers. Dr Elaine Swan has received training in counselling skills and the researchers are experienced in qualitative research about food. By employing exploratory research methods and an open structure to the discussions, the researcher will encourage participants to raise themes that are of importance in their own lives, making it clear that activities can stop or be redirected at any time.

WHAT ARE THE POSSIBLE BENEFITS OF TAKING PART?

By taking part in this study you are helping to expand knowledge on food practices in your neighbourhood and council area which can potentially influence future food-related policies. This data will be of potential benefit in informing the agendas of organisations concerned with food distribution within the area.

WILL MY INFORMATION IN THIS STUDY BE KEPT CONFIDENTIAL?

All information collected about you will be kept strictly confidential. Confidentiality, privacy and anonymity will be ensured through strict adherence to the guidelines for storing, managing and processing data set out in the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the UK Data Protection Act 2018.

After the undertaking the research methods, only the researchers will have access to your data. We will keep all personal information about you (e.g. your name and other information about you that can identify you) confidential, that is we will not share it with others. We will also anonymise the written transcript produced by the transcriber. This means that we will remove any personal information.

This research project may involve the use of University of Sussex Zoom. Details of the platform's privacy notice can be found here: [Zoom Privacy Policy](#). All audio-visual data collected will be downloaded and stored securely on a University of Sussex managed storing system, named OneDrive.

WHAT SHOULD I DO IF I WANT TO TAKE PART?

To opt in for the study, please agree to take part by signing the consent form.

WHAT WILL HAPPEN TO THE RESULTS OF THE RESEARCH STUDY?

The results of this research study will be used to inform several academic pieces of work. These may include: articles in published academic journals, academic book chapters, public presentations, conferences and/or events. Copies of any research output will be made freely available to all participants, although participants should note that this process is planned to take place over a 4-year period, with data retained for the length of that period. When writing up the findings from this study, we would like to reproduce some of the views and ideas you shared with us. We will only use anonymised quotes so that although we will use your exact words, we will do our best to ensure you cannot be identified in the publications, although we cannot guarantee this.

WHO IS ORGANISING AND FUNDING THE RESEARCH?

Research will be undertaken by members of the Management Department and Science Policy Research Unit (SPRU) at the University of Sussex. The project is part of a larger UKRI research study entitled 'Transforming Food Systems for Disadvantaged Communities', which is administered at the University of Reading.

WHO HAS APPROVED THIS STUDY?

The study has been approved by the Social Sciences & Arts Cross-Schools Research Ethics Committee (SSARTA) at the University of Sussex. The ethical review application numbers is [XX/XXXX/X].

CONTACT FOR FURTHER INFORMATION

If you require any additional information, please contact Dr Elaine Swan by emailing e.swan@sussex.ac.uk. Any concerns regarding the way in which the study has been conducted should be directed toward [X] (Chair of the C-REC who reviewed the project) by emailing [X].

INSURANCE

The University of Sussex has insurance in place to cover its legal liabilities in respect of this study.

Thank you for taking the time to read this information sheet. Any participation is greatly appreciated.

CONSENT FORM FOR PROJECT PARTICIPANTS

Title of Project: Foodways: Exploring household and community food practices

Name of Researcher and School: Dr Katerina Psarikidou, SPRU, Dr Elaine Swan and Dr Jesse Hsu, School of Management

Please tick
YES NO

- I consent to participate in the following with the researchers – tick as appropriate:
 - fridge/cupboard tours. YES NO
 - cook-alongs. YES NO
 - shop-alongs. YES NO
 - map drawing. YES NO
- I agree to allow the following to be observed, photographed and audio-video recorded:
 - fridge/cupboard tours YES NO
 - cook-alongs. YES NO
 - shop-alongs. YES NO
 - map drawing YES NO
- I agree if relevant to allow the methods to be conducted and audio-recorded via the University of Sussex Zoom, and being stored in the University of Sussex storing systems. YES NO
- I consent to being informed about follow-up research activities and potential participation in future research. YES NO
- I have read the information sheet, had the opportunity to ask questions and I understand the principles, procedures and possible risks involved. YES NO
- I understand that personal data will be used for the purposes of this research study. I understand that such information will be treated strictly confidential and handled in accordance with [Data Protection legislation](#). YES NO
- I understand that any information given by me may be used in future reports, academic articles, publications or presentations by the researcher and the project team, but my personal information will not be included YES NO
- I understand that data will be kept according to the university guidelines for a minimum of 10 years after the end of the study. YES NO
- I understand that my participation is voluntary, that I can choose not to participate in part or all of the project, and that I can withdraw at any stage of the project without being penalised or disadvantaged in any way. YES NO

• I agree to take part in the above University of Sussex research project

Name:

Signature:

Date:

UNIVERSITY
OF SUSSEX

CHECKLIST: VERBAL CONSENT FROM RESEARCH PARTICIPANTS
FOR RESEARCHER USE ONLY¹

Title of Project: Foodways: Exploring household and community food practices

Name of Researcher and School: Dr Katerina Psarikidou, SPRU, Dr Elaine Swan and Dr Jesse Hsu, School of Management

C-REC Ref no: <Insert ER no.>

A. Process of obtaining verbal consent from research participants:

- 1) Give an account of how you will verbally **explain** to the research participants as clearly as possible and in terms that they are familiar with:
 - The **aims** and **objectives** of your research;
 - The reasons why you have **selected** them for this research;
 - The reasons why their story/knowledge/understanding/opinions are **relevant** to your research;
 - The ways in which the research data will be **used**: for example, in a dissertation/thesis/publications/blogs/reports/policy documents.

Our research study, "Foodways" explores how you do your food provisioning, shopping, preparation and cooking. We are part of a larger multi-university government-funded project on improving access to healthy food in the UK. You have been selected as a participant because you are a resident of one of the communities that we are researching your expertise and experience with cooking and food shopping is important to us because knowledge is can inform future food policies. The research data collected for this project may be used for one or more of the following purposes: for research reports, journal publications, book chapters, conference and workshop presentations, policy documents, blog posts, and food product development.

- 2) I will **verbally explain** to the research participants:
 - That they can **withdraw** from the research at any time without giving a reason, and without being penalised or disadvantaged in any way and/or that they can tell me not to use certain types of information at any time;

¹ To be submitted as supporting documentation for ethical review and approval

Template approved by URGC May 2018

Name of Project and Version No. for Consent Form

What **confidentiality** means in the context of the research and how confidentiality will be maintained in this particular context (OR explain why confidentiality cannot be maintained in this particular case – e.g. focus group);

What **anonymity** means and how it will be maintained in this particular context (OR I will ask approval for the use of their name/location/company/organisation in the final report/dissertation/further publication).

3) Describe below how you will **verbally explain** to your informants that they can **withdraw** from the research at any time, what **confidentiality** and **anonymity** mean in your research context, and how you will explain these terms to your informants:

You may choose to withdraw from our research study at any point without having to provide us a reason. There will be no penalty to do so. You may also ask us to not use any data — recorded conversation, photograph, observation notes— for the study or future research outputs such as journal articles, book chapters, conference presentations, policy reports, until September 1st 2022 when we begin our analysis.

We will try to protect your anonymity but we cannot guarantee it because the photographs and recordings may contain images of objects which could potentially identify you. We will ensure written texts will not contain any identifiable features such as names, occupations, and detailed personal information unless you consent to these. Your names will be anonymised in our research databases order to protect your identity. All data collected for this project will be stored on a secure application called OneDrive which is licensed for the University of Sussex. Project passwords contain at least eight alphanumeric characters and stored on secure university storage systems. Once uploaded to OneDrive, all original data files will be deleted from researcher storage devices. All data files will be named using anonymous IDs.

Our video recordings and photographs will not include identifiable characteristics or images as much as is possible.

4) I will verbally **check** with the research participants that (tick, as applicable):

- They are happy to be interviewed and/or observed by me;
- They are happy for me to be present at and/or participate in their activities;
- They are happy for me to take notes on the interview/observations/interactions;
- They are happy for the interview/observation/interaction to be:

- photographed
- video taped
- audio taped

They are happy to be contacted again for a further interview should that be required.

- 5) I will give the research participants the opportunity to **ask any questions** about any of the above or any other concerns they may have.
- 6) I understand that seeking verbal consent will involve explaining all I have documented above and that verbal consent is an ongoing process. I understand that I will need to document the ongoing process of verbal consent.

B. Researcher Training and Consultation of Professional Guidelines

- 1) I confirm that in the course of my research design, I have received the following training in the ethical aspects of my research (please give details of any modules, CPD or other research ethics training you have attended in the last 18 months):

Two of us teach research methods and regularly update our teaching materials to cover debates and procedures on ethics in line with professional ethical guidelines.

- 2) I confirm that I have read and carefully considered the ethical guidelines of the main professional associations for my subject area (e.g.: the ASA ethical guidelines: <https://www.theasa.org/ethics/guidelines.shtml>) and incorporated them into my research design.

Researcher Signature:

Date: